
LEARNING GEOGRAPHICAL CONCEPTS IN ENGLISH AND FORMING INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS

Xoshimova Dilnoza Sobit qizi

Student of Alfraganus University

dxoshimova8@gmail.com

Annotation: As we all know, interdisciplinary communication is the most important part of the educational process is one of the parts. Interdisciplinary communication is being studied by students forms a permanent attachment to the material and the educational process in general, and every helps them find their way in any field. The information presented in this methodical guide is very useful for geography teachers. At a time when English is the demand of the times, the teaching of geographical information in English in geography classes is not only for students, but also for science. It is also the achievement of teachers. This is the reason for this methodical recommendation there is no doubt that the use of data will ensure that the target is effective.

Key word: Geography, location, map, river, ocean, sea, lake, desert

It is now important in modern education within the system-activity approach has a task. This is the formation of a child's vision of the whole picture of the world, its unity and diversity. This concept refers to the idea of integration is based on interdisciplinarity in educating and teaching students. Implementation of interdisciplinary relations in the comprehensive development of students, helps to achieve great results in the harmonious development of all areas of their intellectual and emotional activity. The main importance of interdisciplinary relations is that they allow to connect all the knowledge obtained in different "subjects" into a single system and to obtain new knowledge based on these connections. Advantages of integrated education: Integrated lessons are a powerful stimulant of the child's mental activity. Children begin to analyze,

compare, look for connections between objects and events, logic, reasoning and communication develop their abilities. To a greater extent than usual, they speak development, formation of skills, generalization, conclusions helps release. The form of conducting integrated classes is non-standard, exciting. The use of different types of work will increase the attention of students keeps at the level, which allows us to talk about the effectiveness of the development of such classes. They relieve the fatigue and excess tension of students due to the transition to different types of activities, cognitive sharply increases interest, imagination, attention of schoolchildren, serves to develop thinking, speech and memory. Integrated lessons often come with discoveries and discoveries. This is a scientific activity in a sense. The special importance of this event is the role of researchers students do. This type of lessons shows the creative potential of the teacher is the oldest method of disclosure. This is not only a teacher's profession a new stage in his career, but also a great opportunity to raise his relationship with the class to a new level. Integrated lessons aim to develop the student's imaginative thinking. In this manual the importance of teaching geography lessons by creating a connection with the English language is illustrated with examples. Also, a table of English names of geographical terms is presented, which includes the necessary terms that can be used in lessons.

The connection of a foreign language with other subjects is diverse and multifunctional. "Foreign language" includes knowledge in various fields: geography, history, social sciences, literature, physics, chemistry, biology, computer science, music, fine arts and other school subjects, etc. It is not an exaggeration to say that it is impossible to study geography without the integration of English. The English language, which has penetrated into every household in the world, is attracting everyone today. Because it is the language of the world. No wonder today President Shavkat Mirziyoyev speaks English they do not create much attention and opportunities. Those who know the language know. In order to conquer the world, we need to know its language. Taking this into account, the

importance of a foreign language, especially English, is increasing for the education of young people with modern knowledge and experience. And it is becoming the need of the hour for every subject to create foreign language integration in their lessons. The main goals of these lessons are to develop students' cognitive interest, to successfully form universal educational activities, and to create conditions for mega-topic results.

is to create.

Below are the English translations of the geographical concepts within the given category:

Accommodation:

Region

Capital

Village

District

City

Geographical points:

Cliff

Hill

Mountain

Plato

Valley

Volcano

Types of natural zones:

Deserts

Forest

Swamp

Tropics

Tundra

Reservoirs:

Ocean

Sea

Lake

River

Flow

It goes without saying that within the scope of this methodological recommendation we cannot list all the names of geographical objects in English, but I will try to mention the geographical names that can be repeated the most.

Continental names:

Africa [frika] - Afrika

Australia [D streili:a] - Avstraliya

Antarctica ['n'ta:ktika] - Antarktida

Eurasia

North America

South America

It's no secret that visual aids play a very important role in geography lessons. For this reason, giving the names of geographical terms through pictures is also very useful in the lesson. It opens the way for students to be more active and acquire knowledge easily.

Exercises can also be created based on the given pictures. For example, if we take the "Pair" exercise, you can match the pictures with the translations of the words in the picture. The above information will greatly help to connect the geography lesson with the English language and make the lesson effective. Undoubtedly, such lessons require special preliminary preparation, but they are very interesting for children. Preparation for such lessons mobilizes students to independent research activities, additional literature and creates the need to work with other sources of information.

References:

1. Зотеева И.Н. "Пути реализации и перспективы использования междпредметных связей". М.: Просвещение, 1991
2. Зотеева И.Н. *Использование междпредметных связей во внеклассной работе" // Иностранные языки в школе.-1990. - No3
3. Xarisova L.V. "Ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida sub'ektlararo alogalar" // Maktabda chet tillari. -1980.-